

**THE INFLUENCE OF SUFISM ON THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT
OF THE SOCIAL-PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF SHAIKH SADI SHERAZI**

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ANNOTATION: This article discusses the influence of Sufism on the formation and development of the socio-philosophical views of Sheikh Saadi Shirazi.

Keywords: the essence of social-philosophical content, human perfection, moral judgments, moral views, universal values, the structure of self-awareness, teacher and student etiquette.

This thesis is dedicated to the moral views of Saadi Shirazy, and it discusses the socio-philosophical content of Saadi Shirazy's moral didactics and the relevance of moral considerations on human perfection from the point of view of contemporary discourse. In addition, interactive technologies in the teaching of this subject are analyzed and methodological recommendations and comments are presented.

Constant attention is paid to the study of social-philosophical, religious-mystical, and humanistic problems in the improvement of the spiritual-ethical image of the peoples of the world, strengthening the positive attitude of society members, especially young people, to universal values through moral and ethical ideas. In particular, the stages of spiritual maturity in the moral teachings of the mystic Saadi Shirazi, who made a significant contribution to the development of Sufism, the structure of human self-awareness in social existence, the manners of a teacher and a student, moral principles, the analysis of the idea of goodness, "egoism", "moral corruption" that is deeply rooted in the process of globalization ", "xenophobia" is gaining constructive importance in fighting evils. Extensive research is being conducted in world science to study the spiritual heritage of Eastern thinkers. Today, such studies are acquiring a posthumanist essence for the development of cultural integration processes and the preservation of universal philosophical traditions.

Before the Arab conquests and for a long time after, the social development of the peoples of Iran and the neighbors of Central Asia faced political and cultural fevers, the consequences of

which led to inevitable crises. Nevertheless, the sense of historical identity and continuity of these peoples prevailed, if not for long, but it was the rebirth of Persia as a central cultural, spiritual, and political player on a regional or even global scale. The period known as the "Renaissance" in European traditions (XV-XVIII centuries) began in the Muslim East, according to A. Metz, in the IX century. The very title of his book "The Muslim Renaissance" speaks about this unique phenomenon. Some researchers associate the medieval cultural period with Islam after the difficult years of anarchy in the first decades of the Arab conquest or even after the collapse of the Sassanids, and the Renaissance in Iran and Central Asia. He believes that it corresponds to the IX to XII centuries. Undoubtedly, the culture of Central Asia and Iran is getting rid of the spiritual and political tyranny imposed by Baghdad, feeding on the rich traditions of Asian cultural influence, which will later allow it to occupy an important place. history of world civilization and world culture. The characteristics of medieval Islam in the region can also be divided into two stages: IX-XII and XIV-XV centuries. Ancient Sogdian, Bactrian, Margiana, Fergana, Khorezm, Parthian or Choch culture had a good perspective to be the necessary conditions for the development of culture.

For example, by the end of the X century, the Seljuks, who settled on the left bank of the Syrdarya, gradually conquered the areas around present-day Samarkand. Around the same time, these tribes converted to Sunni Islam, although they retained many of their traditions and beliefs, but they were contenders for power along with other dynasties such as the Qarakhanids, the Ghaznavids, and the Samanids. Or, the author of "Ancient Civilizations" draws attention to such features as the development of Central Asian culture in the interaction of different cultures and peoples in the region or close contact with the centers of ancient civilizations. The societies of Central Asia and Iran have lived in good relations since ancient times and maintained social, economic, political, and cultural ties with their neighbors. The mass unified culture in the regions of Central Asia and Iran was composed of the nomadic subcultures of the desert peoples of Bactria, Sogd, Khorezm, Fergani, and Margyan, as well as the values and traditions of folk cultures from time immemorial.

Thus, we see that describing the entire medieval Near and Middle Eastern culture as "Arab" has led some studies to ignore the rich ancient spiritual history of the conquered peoples, including the Persians, and their contribution to the world Islamic civilization. The fact that religious, literary poetic, and sometimes historical treatises and inscriptions were written mainly in Arabic in a certain classic medieval period does not mean that the essence and content of the cultural creation of these peoples remained Arabic. Rather, the culture of the peoples of Central

Asia and Iran during these periods of development is not the culture of the Arabs, but the culture of the Muslims of Central Asia, Iran, or other countries that are part of the Arab caliphate.

One of the characteristics of the culture of Central Asia and Iran is the geographical location of the region, on one hand, the climate, on the one hand, the presence of three great civilizations in the neighborhood of Mesopotamia, India, and China, was an intermediary in the middle. While serving as a bridge in trade and cultural exchange between the West and the East, [30; 143]

In Islam, it is possible to distinguish such periods, which correspond to the stages of spiritual inner evolution, i.e. Qualitative changes in Islamic culture and system: prophethood-Qur'an era; an era of ideological differences or "limited pluralism"; 3) the formation of regional forms of Islamic existence, which absorbed many elements of the spiritual heritage of the Islamic nations.

This area was called Moverannahr (beyond the river) by the Arab invaders. historical sources recorded it as a rich region with invaluable material and spiritual achievements, but the Arabs destroyed many cultural monuments, including libraries, and burned many books and manuscripts written by local thinkers in the local language and script. Zoroastrian temples and holy places were destroyed. According to Beruni's "Memorials of Past Generations", the Arabs killed representatives of the local clergy and burned their valuable works of art and literature. They destroyed historical documents in Sogd, Khorezm, Samarkand, and Bukhara. When there are enough valid facts and reasons to emphasize that the Persian-speaking culture has experienced the worst decline, decline, repression, and oppression, but after a short period, it was able to revive and restore the national spirituality and culture concerning intelligence. and along with knowledge, they certainly refer to the great values and traditions of their ancestors. They made great efforts to strengthen the spiritual-intellectual foundation of Islamic culture, which combines reason, morality, and faith.

However, the role of the rulers of the Abbasid dynasty, who sponsored the development of science and art, in the Muslim Renaissance cannot be ignored. Harun-ar-Rashid (786-809) and his son Ma'mun, intending to raise the prestige of science, gathered many scientists in Baghdad and created conditions for them in the academy - "Baytul-hikma". The socio-political situation in the region improved, and the cities of Bukhara, Samarkand, Termiz, Khiva, Khojand, Fergana, and Kokand became cultural centers. Mamun Academy in Khorezm also contributed to the development of science and art. In addition, in terms of economy, the Great Silk Road played an important role.

Philosophical, ethical, and religious sciences developed rapidly in the countries of Central Asia and Iran during the Renaissance period of the X and XII centuries. But they did not become the same and natural.

According to one of the Western researchers, the universal meaning of the word "Islam" cannot be limited by the boundaries of national or ethnic boundaries to have a clear picture of the society and its state at the time of its emergence.

Under the influence of various ideologies associated with the Muslim world, various elements have entered Sufism, but it is still necessary to clarify this complex issue.

Of course, Gnostic, Manichean Neoplatonic, and similar phenomena in Sufism can be announced, but this is not enough to clarify the essence. It is necessary to explain the conditions that created the advantage of the above phenomena to enter Sufism. After that, information can be given about Sufism, its historical place, and further development.

It can be said that Sufism as a way of spiritual perfection appeared at the end of the VII century and the beginning of the 8th century. By the XI century, Sufism began to be explained as a new movement consisting of the ideologies of ancient Eastern views.

Sufism: "It was created under the leadership of prominent people such as Abu Abdullah Kharis ibn Asad al-Anazi al-Mukhasibi (Baghdad, lived before 857), Abdul Fayd ibn Ibrahim Zunnun al-Misri (lived before 860), Abu Hafs Omar ibn Salma. al-Haddad (died before 878), Abu Salih Hamdun al-Kossar (died before 871), Abu Osman Sa'd ibn Ismail al-Khiri (died before 910-11), Abdul Qasim ibn Muhammad al-Junaid (lived until 911)), Husain ibn al-Mansur al-Hallaj (858-922), Imam Abu Hamid Muhammad ibn Muhammad Ghazoli (1059/60-1111), Abu Said ibn Abdul Khair (967-1049)" [38; 164].

Sufism can be said: the manifestation of scientific theology and rationalism: is the revival of ancient Gnosticism. These include the institution of mystery, the theory of the emergence of God, esotericism, the parallel existence of two worlds, asceticism and libertinism, and their mutual transformation, and the concept of a specific "path" of the soul and its salvation. Sufism did not deny the possibility of merging with God, they took seriously Sufism and its terminology: purity of thought, suffering and love, partnership and aspiration.

The reason for the rapid spread of Sufism was the Arab caliphate and its social conditions. The consequences of this spread were varied and profound changes in Sufi doctrine. To understand the reasons for the emergence of Sufism as a phenomenon in the Islamic world, one must first have a clear idea of the society and its situation at the time of its emergence. Under the influence of various ideologies associated with the Muslim world, various elements have entered

Sufism, but it is still necessary to clarify this complex issue.

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